

**BO‘LAJAK O‘QITUVCHILARNI “KRISTALL JISMLAR TUZILISHI” MAVZUSINI
KO‘RGAZMALILIK ASOSIDA O‘QITISHDA MAPLE DASTURIY VOSITASIDAN
FOYDALANISHGA TAYYORLASH**

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Barchamizga juda yaxshi ma’lumki, axborot kommunikatsion texnologiyalari hamda dasturiy vositalar kirib bormagan soha qolmadi. Ularning imkoniyatlari hayotimizni yengillatishi, qulayliklar yaratishi bilan birga hayotimizning ajralmas qismiga aylanishga ham ulgurdi. Boshqa sohalarda bo‘lgani kabi ta’lim sohasida ham axborot texnologiyalari imkoniyatlaridan foydalangan holda o‘quv jarayonini tashkil etish yurtimizning barcha ta’lim muassasalarida allaqachon an’anaga aylanib ulgurdi deydi barcha bo‘lsak ham aslo mubolag‘a bo‘lmaydi. Shular qatorida akademik litseylarida ham barcha fanlar kabi fizika darslarini ham proyektor, elektron doska, kompyuter jixozlari, internet tarmog‘i, virtual laboratoriyalar, gipermediya imkoniyatlari bilan bir qatorda har bir dars uchun mo‘ljallangan dars taqdimotlari va dasturiy vosita yordamida olingan turli ishlanmalar yordamida tashkil qilish hozirgi kunning talabiga aylangan. Shunga asosan fizika fanining tushunish va tasavvur qilishda qiyinchiliklar tug‘diradigan mavzular sirasiga kiradigan kristall jismlarning ichki tuzilishi bilan bog‘liq mavzusini zamonaviy Maple dasturiy vositasida yoritishga harakat qilamiz.

Akademik litsey o‘quv dasturi bo‘yicha 1-bosqich o‘quvchilariga bahorda moddalarning ichki xususiyatlari, moddalarning tuzilishi degan bobda kristall jismlarning stukturalari hamda yacheyka turlari haqidagi ma’lumotlar o‘qitiladi. Moddaning bir-biriga yaqin joylashgan bir nechta atom yoki molekulalari fazoviy biror shakl hosil qiladi. Bu shaklni yacheyka deb atalib, yacheyka turlari juda ham xilma-xildir. Masalan, atom yoki molekulalar markazlari jubning qirralarida joylashgan bo‘lsa, uni kubik yacheyka deb, agar olti qirrali prizma uchlarida joylashgan bo‘lsa, uni geksonal yacheyka deb ataladi. Kubik va geksonal yacheykalar ham o‘z navbatida markazlashgan kubik yoki geksonal hamda yoqlari markazlashgan kubik yoki geksonal kabi turlarga bo‘linadi. Undan tashqari qirralari og‘ma kubik, geksonal, rombaedrik va hokoza turlari mavjud bo‘lib, ularni o‘quvchilarga odiygina og‘zaki (oral) tushuntirish uncha samara bermaydi. Kristallar va yacheykalarni zamonaviy dasturlar yordamida hosil qilingan fazoviy tasvirlarini darsdan uzoqlashmagan holda, mavzuni o‘tish jarayonida parallel ravishda ko‘rgazmali materiallar sifatida ko‘rsatib, namoyish etib o‘tish darsning ta’sirchanligi hamda unumdorligini oshirishga sabab bo‘ladi [1,328].

Shu maqsadda biz imkoniyati nihoyatda keng bo‘lgan Maple dasturiy paketiga murojaat qilishimiz mumkin. Kristall yacheykalardagi atom yoki molekula joylashgan nuqtani tugunlar deymiz. Keling, soddaroq bo‘lishi uchun tugunda faqat atomlar o‘tiribdi deb olib, uni sharsimon qilib tasvirlaylik. Maple paketida sharni **sphere** buyrug‘i bilan kiritiladi. Masalan, markazi koordinata boshida bo‘lgan, radiusi 3 ga teng bo‘lgan va rangi qizil bo‘lgan sferani chizish uchun **sphere(0,0,0,3,color=red)** buyrug‘i bilan kiritiladi. Yacheyka qanday shaklda ekanini yaqqol tasvirlash uchun yacheyka tugunlarini kesmalar bilan tutashtirib chiqish kerak. Maple paketida kesmalar **line** buyrug‘i bilan kiritiladi. Masalan, uchlari (-1,-2,-3) va (1,2,3) nuqtalarda joylashgan, rangi jigarrang bo‘lgan, qalinligi 3 ga teng bo‘lgan kesmani **line([-1,-2,-3], [1,2,3], color=brown, thickness=3)** buyrug‘i bilan kiritiladi. Mana shu ikkita buyruq bilan oddiy

yacheykalar va kristall tugunlarining 3d o‘lchamli tasvirlarini olishimiz mumkin. Buning uchun Dekart koordinatalar sistemasidan foydalanamiz va har bir tugundagi atom (sfera) ni koordinatalari hamda tugunlarni tutashtiruvchi kesmalar koordinatalarini kiriritish uchun algoritm tuzish kerak bo‘ladi. Bir-biri bilan farqlash uchun har bir chiziqni $l1, l2, l3...$ kabi va har bir sferani $s1, s2, s3,...$ kabi nomerlab olgan ma’qul. Chizmalarni ekranga chiqarish uchun **plots[display](l1,l2,l3,...,s1,s2,s3,...)**; buyrug‘idan foydalanamiz. Eng avvalo eng oddiy yacheyka – markazlashgan kubikni 3d o‘lchamli tasvirini olish uchun Maple-12 dasturiy paketidan foydalanib algoritm tuzaylik.

> with(plottools) :

> a := 4; R := a/5;

$$a := 4 \quad R := \frac{4}{5}$$

> l1 := line([-a/2,-a/2,-a/2], [-a/2, a/2,-a/2], color = black) :
 l2 := line([-a/2, a/2,-a/2], [a/2, a/2,-a/2], color = black) :

l3 := line([a/2, a/2,-a/2], [a/2,-a/2,-a/2], color = black) : l4
 := line([a/2,-a/2,-a/2], [-a/2,-a/2,-a/2], color = black) :
 l5 := line([-a/2,-a/2, a/2], [-a/2, a/2, a/2], color = black) : l6 := line([-a/2, a/2, a/2], [a/2, a/2, a/2], color = black) :

l7 := line([a/2, a/2, a/2], [a/2,-a/2, a/2], color = black) : l8
 := line([a/2,-a/2, a/2], [-a/2,-a/2, a/2], color = black) :

l9 := line([-a/2,-a/2,-a/2], [-a/2,-a/2, a/2], color = black) :
 l10 := line([-a/2, a/2,-a/2], [-a/2, a/2, a/2], color = black) :

l11 := line([a/2, a/2,-a/2], [a/2, a/2, a/2], color = black) : l12
 := line([a/2,-a/2,-a/2], [a/2,-a/2, a/2], color = black) :

> c1 := sphere([-a/2,-a/2,-a/2], R, color = red) : c2 := sphere([-a/2, a/2,-a/2], R, color = red) :
 c3 := sphere([a/2, a/2,-a/2], R, color = red) : c4 := sphere([a/2,-a/2,-a/2], R, color = red) :
 c5 := sphere([-a/2,-a/2, a/2], R, color = red) : c6 := sphere([-a/2, a/2, a/2], R, color = red) :
 c7 := sphere([a/2, a/2, a/2], R, color = red) : c8 := sphere([a/2,-a/2, a/2], R, color = red) : c9 := sphere([0, 0, 0], R, color = blue) :

> plots[display](l1, l2, l3, l4, l5, l6, l7, l8, l9, l10, l11, l12, c1, c2, c3, c4, c5, c6, c7, c8, c9, scaling = constrained, axes = normal, style = wireframe, thickness = 3);

Shunda bizga kompyuter dasturi 1-a.rasmdagi tasvirni chiqaradi. Bu markazlashgan kubik yacheykasining 3d o‘lchamli tasviri bo‘lib, kub qirralaridagi atomni qizil rangda, markazidagi atomni esa ko‘k rangda tasvirlandi. Agar xuddi shunday usulda bir nechta yonmayon joylashgan yacheykalarni dasturga kiritsak, u holda kristal tuzilishiga oid 3d o‘lchamli tasvirga ega bo‘lamiz (1-b,rasm).

1-rasm

Endi kubik yacheykaning biroz murakkabroq ko‘rinishini, ya’ni yoqlari markazlashgan kubikni tasvirlashga harakat qilaylik. Bunda bitta yacheykada kubning uchlarida 8 ta, kub yoqlarining markazlarida 6 ta atom joylashgan bo‘lib, jami 14 ta atom bitta yoqlari markazlashgan yacheykani hosil qiladi. Ana shu yacheykani hosil qilsih uchun algoritm tuzaylik.

> *with(plottools)* :

> $a := 4$; $R := a/5$;

$$a := 4$$
$$R := \frac{4}{5}$$

```

> l1 := line([-a/2,-a/2,-a/2],[ -a/2, a/2,-a/2], color = black) :
    l2 := line([-a/2, a/2,-a/2],[ a/2, a/2,-a/2], color
    = black) :
    l3 := line([a/2, a/2,-a/2],[ a/2,-a/2,-a/2], color = black) : l4
    := line([a/2,-a/2,-a/2],[ -a/2,-a/2,-a/2], color = black) :
    l5 := line([-a/2,-a/2, a/2],[ -a/2, a/2, a/2], color
    = black) : l6 := line([-a/2, a/2, a/2],[ a/2, a/2, a/2], color
    = black) :
    l7 := line([a/2, a/2, a/2],[ a/2,-a/2, a/2], color = black) : l8
    := line([a/2,-a/2, a/2],[ -a/2,-a/2, a/2], color = black) :
    l9 := line([-a/2,-a/2,-a/2],[ -a/2,-a/2, a/2], color
    = black) : l10 := line([-a/2, a/2,-a/2],[ -a/2, a/2, a/2],
    color = black) : l11 := line([a/2, a/2,-a/2],[ a/2, a/2, a/2],
    color = black) : l12 := line([a/2,-a/2,-a/2],[ a/2,-a/2, a
    /2], color = black) :

> c1 := sphere([-a/2,-a/2,-a/2], R, color = red) : c2 := sphere([
    -a/2, a/2,-a/2], R, color = red) :
    c3 := sphere([a/2, a/2,-a/2], R, color = red) : c4 := sphere([a
    /2,-a/2,-a/2], R, color = red) :
    c5 := sphere([-a/2,-a/2, a/2], R, color = red) : c6 := sphere([
    -a/2, a/2, a/2], R, color = red) :
    c7 := sphere([a/2, a/2, a/2], R, color = red) : c8 := sphere([a
    /2,-a/2, a/2], R, color = red) :
    c9 := sphere([0, 0, a/2], R, color = blue) : c10 := sphere([0,
    a/2, 0], R, color = blue) :
    c11 := sphere([0, 0,-a/2], R, color = blue) : c12 := sphere([0,
    -a/2, 0], R, color = blue) : c13 := sphere([-a/2, 0, 0], R,
    color = blue) : c14 := sphere([a/2, 0, 0], R, color = blue) :

> plots[display](l1, l2, l3, l4, l5, l6, l7, l8, l9, l10, l11, l12, c1, c2, c3,
    c4, c5, c6, c7, c8, c9, c10, c11, c12, c13, c14, scaling
    = constrained, axes = normal, style = wireframe, thickness = 2);
    
```

Shunda bizga kompyuter dasturi 2-a, rasmdagi tasvirni hosil qiladi. Bu yoqlari markazlashgan kubik yacheykasining 3d o'lchamli tasviri bo'lib, kub qirralaridagi 8 ta atomni qizil rangda, yoqlari markazidagi 6 ta atomni esa ko'k rangda tasvirlandi. Agar xuddi shunday usulda dasturdagi algoritmi kengaytirib, qo'shni bir nechta yacheykalarni ham dasturga tugunlardagi atomlarning koordinatalarini berish orqali dasturga kiritsak, u holda yoqlari markazlashgan kubik yacheykali kristal tuzilishiga oid 3d o'lchamli tasvirga ega bo'lamiz (2-b, rasm).

2-rasm

Kristall yacheykalarining yana bir ken tarqalgan ko‘rinishi – bu geksonal (6 qirrali) yacheykadir. Bunda 6 burchakli prizmaning yuqorigi va pastki uchlarida 6 tadan atom joylashgan bo‘ladi. Undan tashqari markazlashgan yoki yoqlari markazlashgan geksonal yacheyka ekanligiga qarab prizma markazida yoki prizmaning 3 ta yon yog‘i markazida 1 tadan qo‘shimcha atomlar joylashgan bo‘ladi. Prizma uchlaridagi atomlarni qizil rangda, markazidagi atomni ko‘k rangda tasvirlashga harakat qilaylik. Mana shu markazlashgan geksonal yacheyka uchun algoritm tuzaylik [5,105]. .

> *with(plottools)* :

> $a := 4; R := a/3; H := 2*a;$

$a := 4$

$R := \frac{4}{3}$

$H := 8$

> $l1 := \text{line}([a, 0, -H/2], [a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$
 $l2 := \text{line}([a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], [-a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$
 $l3 := \text{line}([-a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], [-a, 0, -H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$
 $l4 := \text{line}([-a, 0, -H/2], [-a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$
 $l5 := \text{line}([-a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], [a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$
 $l6 := \text{line}([a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], [a, 0, -H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$
 $l7 := \text{line}([a, 0, H/2], [a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$
 $l8 := \text{line}([a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], [-a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$
 $l9 := \text{line}([-a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], [-a, 0, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

$l10 := \text{line}([-a, 0, H/2], [-a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black})$
 $l11 := \text{line}([-a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], [a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

$l12 := \text{line}([a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], [a, 0, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

$l13 := \text{line}([a, 0, -H/2], [a, 0, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

$l14 := \text{line}([a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], [a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

$l15 := \text{line}([-a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], [-a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

$l16 := \text{line}([-a, 0, -H/2], [-a, 0, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

$l17 := \text{line}([-a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], [-a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

$l18 := \text{line}([a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], [a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], \text{color} = \text{black}) :$

> $c1 := \text{sphere}([a, 0, -H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c2 := \text{sphere}([a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c3 := \text{sphere}([-a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c4 := \text{sphere}([-a, 0, -H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c5 := \text{sphere}([-a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c6 := \text{sphere}([a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, -H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c7 := \text{sphere}([a, 0, H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c8 := \text{sphere}([a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c9 := \text{sphere}([-a/2, -\sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c10 := \text{sphere}([-a, 0, H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c11 := \text{sphere}([-a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c12 := \text{sphere}([a/2, \sqrt{3}/2 * a, H/2], R, \text{color} = \text{red}) :$
 $c13 := \text{sphere}([0, 0, 0], R, \text{color} = \text{blue}) :$

$\text{plots}[\text{display}](l1, l2, l3, l4, l5, l6, l7, l8, l9, l10, l11, l12, l13, l14, l15, l16, l17, l18, c1, c2, c3, c4, c5, c6, c7, c8, c9, c10, c11, c12, c13, \text{scaling} = \text{constrained}, \text{axes} = \text{normal}, \text{style} = \text{wireframe}, \text{thickness} = 2);$

3-rasm

Shunda bizga kompyuter dasturi 3-a,rasmdagi tasvirni hosil qiladi. Agar xuddi shunday usulda dasturdagi algoritmni kengaytirib, qo‘shni bir nechta yacheykalarni ham dasturga koordinatalarini kiritish orqali algoritm tuzsak, u holda yoqlari markazlashgan geksonal yacheykali kristal tuzilishiga oid 3d o‘lchamli tasvirga ega bo‘lamiz (3-b,rasm).

Xuddi syuqoridagiga o‘xshash tarzda yoqlari markazlashgan kubik yacheykani 3d o‘lchamli tasvirini olish uchun Maple-12 dasturiy paketidan foydalanib algoritm tuzishimiz mumkin.

```
> with(plottools) :
> a := 4; R := a/3; H := 2*a;
```

```
a := 4
R := 4/3
H := 8
```

```

> l1 := line([a, 0, -H/2], [a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], color = black) :
    l2 := line([a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], [-a/2, -sqrt(3)/2
    *a, -H/2], color = black) :    l3 := line([-a/2, -sqrt(3)/2
    *a, -H/2], [-a, 0, -H/2], color = black) :    l4 := line([-a, 0,
    -H/2], [-a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], color = black) :    l5
    := line([-a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], [a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2],
    color = black) :    l6 := line([a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2],
    [a, 0, -H/2], color = black) :    l7 := line([a, 0, H/2], [a/2,
    -sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], color = black) :    l8 := line([a/2,
    -sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], [-a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], color = black)
    :    l9 := line([-a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], [-a, 0, H/2],
    color = black) :    l10 := line([-a, 0, H/2], [-a/2, sqrt(3)
    /2*a, H/2], color = black) :    l11 := line([-a/2,
    sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], [a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], color = black) :
    l12 := line([a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], [a, 0, H/2],
    color = black) :    l13 := line([a, 0, -H/2], [a, 0, H/2],
    color = black) :    l14 := line([a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], [a/2
    -sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], color = black) :    l15 := line([-a/2,
    -sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], [-a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], color
    = black) :    l16 := line([-a, 0, -H/2], [-a, 0, H/2], color
    = black) :    l17 := line([-a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], [-a
    /2, sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], color = black) :    l18 := line([a
    /2, sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], [a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], color = black)
    :
    
```

```

> c1 := sphere([a, 0, -H/2], R, color = red) :    c2
    := sphere([a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], R, color = red) :
    c3 := sphere([-a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], R, color = red) : c4
    := sphere([-a, 0, -H/2], R, color = red) :
    c5 := sphere([-a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], R, color = red) : c6
    := sphere([a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, -H/2], R, color = red) :
    c7 := sphere([a, 0, H/2], R, color = red) :    c8
    := sphere([a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], R, color = red) :
    c9 := sphere([-a/2, -sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], R, color = red) : c10
    := sphere([-a, 0, H/2], R, color = red) :
    c11 := sphere([-a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], R, color = red) : c12
    := sphere([a/2, sqrt(3)/2*a, H/2], R, color = red) : c13
    := sphere([3/4*a, sqrt(3)/4*a, 0], R, color = blue) : c14
    := sphere([-3/4*a, sqrt(3)/4*a, 0], R, color = blue) : c15
    := sphere([0, -sqrt(3)/2*a, 0], R, color = blue) :
    
```

```

> plots[display](l1, l2, l3, l4, l5, l6, l7, l8, l9, l10, l11, l12, l13, l14, l15,
    l16, l17, l18, c1, c2, c3, c4, c5, c6, c7, c8, c9, c10, c11, c12, c13,
    c14, c15, scaling = constrained, axes = normal, style
    = wireframe, thickness = 2);
    
```

Shunda bizga kompyuter dasturi 4-a, rasmdagi tasvirni hosil qiladi. Yuqorida bajarilganla kabi markazlashgan geksonal yacheykali kristall pangaralarining 3d o'lichamli tasvirlarini ham Maple paketidan foydalanib osongina hosil qilishimiz mumkin (4-b, rasm).

4-rasm

Albatta bizning birinchi maqsadimiz, dars davomida akademik litsey o‘quvchilariga dasturlashni o‘rgatish bo‘lmasdan, balki fizika faniga tegishli mavzularni o‘rgatishdan iboratdir. Lekin, mavzuning ta’sirchanligi, jozibadorligini oshirish hamda vaqtdan unumli foydalanish maqsadida turli dasturiy vositalar va paketlar yordamida olingan har xil ishlanmalardan fizikaga oid mavzuni yoritish davomida parallel hoda foydalangan ma’quldir. Bu esa mavzuni o‘quvchilar tomonidan tushinishlari va o‘zlashtirishlari, mavzuga oid hodisa va jarayonlarni yaqqol ko‘z oldiga keltira olishlari bo‘yicha ko‘nikma va malakalarini oshishiga olib keladi.

Shunday qilib, kristall jismlarni tuzilishiga oid mavzuni zamonaviy dasturiy vositalar yordamida o‘quvchilarga o‘qitish yuqorida sanab o‘tilgan afzalliklarga ega bo‘lishidan tashqari, o‘quvchilarni dasturlar bilan ishlashga qiziqish uyg‘otar, mustqil o‘zlari ishlashlari uchun imkn yaratar ekan. Undan tashqari o‘qituvchi tomonidan molekula va atomlar orasidagi tortishish va itarishish kuchlari mavjudligi tufayli yacheyka tugunlaridagi atom va molekulalar qotib qolgan holda turmasdan, shu tugun atrofida tebranib turishlarini hamda bu tebranma harakat kuchayganda asta-sekin suyuqlikka aylanish boshlanishlarini ham mazkur mavzuda tushuntirib o‘tilishi mumkin. Bu esa o‘quvchilarning bilimlarini atoflicha, chuqur shakllanishiga oilb keladi.

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